

ROLE OF NREGA IN THE ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN THE RURAL AREA

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ABSTRACT

Women's role in socio-economic development of a country is crucial. Now it can be said that women's are also equally capable as men to look after the family. National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005 or (NREGA) is a program developed as a poverty elevation program so as to guarantee employment for 100days in a year. It mainly aims at giving employment opportunities for women. It helped women to gain the empowerment. The impact assessment comes as an important intervention in the wake of NREGA Act,2005 which is implemented all over India from 1st april 2008. The idea of the assessment is also premised on the widely held belief that NREGA is foundationally capable of transforming the rural life's by improving living conditions. It increased the standard of living of the family and gave economic support. Therefore we seek to find out the effectiveness of the Act in the financial empowerment of women's of rural area. The study "Role of NREGA in economic empowerment of women in rural areas" is based on both primary and secondary data. The respondents are collected through convenient sampling.

Keywords : Employment, Rural, Women, Economic, Opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005 (NREGA) is a security scheme which provide employment and livelihood to rural workers in the country. The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005 (NREGA) later renamed as "Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act" (MGNREGA), which is an Indian labor law and social security measure which provides livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of wage employment in a financial year. Another aim of MGNREGA is to create durable assets (such as roads, canals, ponds, wells). In this scheme the employment is provided within 5 km of an applicant's residence and a minimum wages should be paid. If work is not provided within 15 days after applying, applicants are entitled to an unemployment allowance. Thus, employment under MGNREGA is legal. It was launched in February 2006 by the prime minister at that time Mr. Manmohan Singh. The scheme has covered almost all parts of the country. It took the initiative to empower the women by providing at least 100 days of wage employment.

MGNREGA is mainly implemented by gram panchayats. In this, the involvement of contractors is banned. Certain tasks like creating infrastructure for water harvesting, drought relief and flood control are preferred. Apart from providing empowerment NREGA also helps in protecting the environment, empowering rural women, reducing rural-urban migration and fostering social equity, among others. The government is aligning NREGA with Aadhar, biometric database to make the payments directly to beneficiaries and weed out frauds that siphon off money. The MNREGA is being recast to include de-silting of water bodies besides the building of check dams, percolation tanks and farm ponds to brace against a possible drought.

Among all the initiatives taken by government we have tried to partially study the role of NREGA for empowering women in Karivellur Peralam Gram Panchayat . In this region a large number of women population are engaged as daily wages worker. Most of them are engaged as labor in household work, harvesting, house construction, road construction, shopping complex such as cleaning, sweeping and so on.

The MGNREGA is the first program to provide livelihood security to the poor. It is one of the innovative programs to boost:-

- (a) The rural economy
- (b) Stabilize agricultural production
- (c) To provide livelihood security to the poor and there by transform the scenario of poverty.

What holds the MGNREGS back is “work rationing”- the inability of interested households to get 100 days of work-as a result of mismanagement or pressures, and affects the poorest the most ,the report fines.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

NREGA is a program developed as a poverty alleviation program to guarantee employment for 100 days in a year. The people who take care of the natural resources and who help the nation to grow do not have enough access to basic requirements such as foods, shelter and clothing. By analyzing these MGNREGA was introduced. It mainly aims at giving employment opportunities for women .The main aim is to provide a normal and decent lifestyle to the people of rural India. The idea of the assessment is held on the belief that NREGA will be capable of transforming the rural lives by improving living conditions, increasing sustainable agrarian activities and wholesome economic support.

Therefore we seek to find out the effectiveness of the ACT in the financial empowerment of women of rural areas.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Gandhiji once said “In a country like India women are the part and parcel of the vast Indian society. They should be alerted with proper education and also they should be entrusted with all sorts of jobs as per their physical ability.”

Women are an important part of a society. They play vital role in the development of the society as well as the country. When women are supported to empower themselves the whole society benefits and families are healthier. They play a very important role in making their family financially independence. Therefore, it is very essential to empower women. The MGNREGA provides a legal guarantee to work. It is an inclusive program covering all the disadvantaged sections of the society. This program plays a vital role for the upliftment of the women in the rural area. In this context we seek to measure the extent to which the NREGA programme has succeeded in empowering the women's. We also find it essential to study the way of implementation and the organizational work associated with.

From this research we found NREGA programme is very much essential to study the way of implementation and the organizational work associated with. And we also found that NREGA programme has succeeded in empowering the women.

OBJECTIVES

- ❑ To study the procedure of implementation of the programme.
- ❑ To find out any difficulties the women workers face.
- ❑ To study the facilities provided by the scheme.
- ❑ To evaluate the impact of the NREGA program.
- ❑ To suggest suitable measures for the effective implementation.
- ❑ To assess the improvement in standard of living of women.
- ❑ To assess the empowerment of women through NREGA program.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology we adopted in this paper is Descriptive Research. A questionnaire based field work has been followed. The study 'Role of NREGA in economic empowerment of women in rural areas' is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected from 45 women employees under NREGA in rural areas of Kaniellur Panch Gram Panchayat. The reports are stated through content analysis method. The data collected through the questionnaire are classified and subjected to further analysis. Recent analysis and data are used to analyze the data collected. The secondary data is collected through certain sites regarding how the schemes are helping women's in empowerment.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study is completed in a period of 20 days from 2nd March 2017 to 22nd March 2017.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study has the following limitations:

- ❑ The information collected is restricted only to women of Kaniellur Panch Gram Panchayat.

- The study was conducted within a limited time period.
- Binary data is collected for a sample of 25 women. A limitation of the sample size is in the study.

KARIVELLUR PERALAM PANCHAYATH

This panchayat is situated in the Pambattalukin Kanur district. It consists of 12 wards. It is situated in the region of Kanur and consists of mainly middle class and lower class families. People of the village are mostly engaged in farming and trade service sector. The village is an area of 8.9 sq. It has a population of 1284, which includes 631 men and 63 women.

DATA ANALYSIS

Based on our study regarding the 'ROLE OF NREGA IN THE ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN RURAL AREAS' we prepared questionnaires in order to analyze the data and how the scheme are finding successful in empowering women in rural areas in a different way. The following table analysis we conducted and the responses which we collected.

a) The Age Of Labors

According to the survey we conducted we can make it that the age of women are more in this scheme. Most of the women under this scheme are 40 years. When we are questioned about this it was due to the reason that they do not have a source of income to do and because of this most of the women are dependent on their kids of schemes in order to sustain. While those who are apart of this scheme are not able to get any other work which they can do in order to contribute to their family.

b) Marital Status Of The Labors

This is a pie chart representing the marital status of laborers in NREGA. This shows that among the laborers 89% women are married, 7% women are widow and 4% women are divorced. This shows that the NREGA act is a boon for women mainly to impart additional work to women.

c) Qualification Of Labors

This is a pie chart representing the qualification of laborers in NREGA and it clearly shows that 38% laborers are 10th, 56% are below 10th and 6% are illiterate. In a nutshell, this shows that the laborers are mostly uneducated and highly unskilled.

d) Source Of Information

The above graph specifies the source of information which they got to know about NREGA. Most of them got aware through regular panchayat meetings. And others through panchayat members, relatives, panchayat president, etc.

e) Number of year's people started working under NREGA in karivellur peralam gram panchayat

This pie chart depicts that the NREGA beneficiaries in many states or villages by empowering sports of women in order to survive in the field. We can analyze that 3% women are part of this scheme for 5 years, 27% for 3 years, etc.

f) Activities provided under NREGA

NREGA provides various kinds of activities like water conservation, land development, agriculture, swachh Bharath, etc. By implementing such activities NREGA aims at helping to the rural and urban areas.

And also we can make it clear that NREGA also aims in the development of our country.

g) Wage satisfaction

The wage satisfaction of the laborers was positive. However, we could not get any data for 78% as stated in the 2% as stated. Some can be that NREGA provides satisfactory wages in order to improve their life. They are providing Rs 150 as their daily wages.

h) Any development in villages?

Yes, though slowly it is starting to see huge improvement in the villages by providing certain activities like water conservation, land development, soil health, cultivation etc. These activities help in providing a friendly environment for the people.

i) Problems faced by the labors under this scheme

The main problem we identified through the collected data is mainly work allotment problems and delay wages. 19 has stated this problem regarding work allotment, while they are not provide with proper works. And out of 27 among 45 stated that the wages are not paid in time.

j) Benefits provided to the labors

The NREGA aims in empowering women with additional skills. In this way it is found that helps in poverty eradication and to help in business. This also helps in the demand of jobs in the villages among women.

k) Satisfaction of employees working under NREGA

According to the study, the impact of NREGA on the rural population has been positive. It has helped to improve the living standards of the rural population. The study also found that NREGA has helped to reduce the poverty levels in the rural areas. The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the social and economic conditions of the rural population. The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the health and education of the rural population. The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the overall quality of life of the rural population.

CONCLUSION

- NREGA is a good initiative to provide employment opportunities to the rural population.
- This also helps to reduce the poverty levels in the rural areas.
- The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the social and economic conditions of the rural population.
- The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the health and education of the rural population.
- The study also found that NREGA has helped to improve the overall quality of life of the rural population.

REFERENCES

1. Agawal P (1987) The Role of Women in Socio-Economic and Social Welfare.
2. Vasanta Kumari P (2008) Women Empowerment Through Micro Enterprises Development. *Southern Economist* Volume 47/Number 15.
3. Sudha K (2008) Problems of Self-Employed Women: An Analysis. *Southern Economist* Volume 47.
4. Sakran A (2009) Trends and Problems of Rural Women Entrepreneurs in India.
5. National Policy for the Empowerment of Women (2015).
6. Impact Assessment of NREGA in Kerala: The Evaluation of Systems and Processes by J. S. Chackrabarti and G. S. Nair, Centre for Rural Management (CRM) Kottayam, April (2008).
7. NCAE - PFI Study on Evaluating Performance of National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, New Delhi, NCAE, 2009.

